

Finally, there is a lack of civil engagement in the reform process. Participation of civil society is a new phenomenon in the post-Soviet region (Tartes, 2016, p. 27). Therefore, the EaP should create awareness of the importance of civil society engagement in reform processes. It should also promote more collaboration between EaP members' and civil societies (Giragosian, 2015, p. 10).

Moreover, the EU continues to face several constraints. The EU's goal of spreading European democratic values is occasionally resisted as they are not fully compatible with the political structure of the EaP members (Tartes, 2016, p. 27). The EU strives to influence the reformation process with positive conditionality, in other words the EaP member must be fully engaged in the democratisation process for it to be eligible for other forms of assistance. Armenia is still very much run by elitists that prevail over democratic institutions while many Soviet and Russian values remained engrained within its society to this day. Therefore, it is not possible to get onto the democratization path overnight. By understanding that democratisation is a slow process and taking into account the domestic political structure, the EU may be able to achieve more in the long run if it does not base its agreements solely on the condition of democratization (Tartes, 2016, p. 32). In addition, the EU becomes constrained in the EaP implementation process by its members since it is ultimately up to each member state to decide on the level of integration (Delcour, 2012, p. 8). Therefore, regardless of how much effort the EU puts in its policies, if the EaP member refuses to oblige, all efforts would be in vain. This was the case when Armenia unilaterally decided to forfeit the AA despite it having been developed since 2010. There is no clear way to overcome this constraint other than by simply building trust between the partners so that all policies will be effectively implemented.

CONCLUSION

From the above discussion we can see that the ENP/EaP has continued to evolve over the years. Armenia and the EU collaborate on varying levels on the issues of democracy, institutional reform and jurisprudence, socio-economic reform and infrastructure development, people-to-people contact, and economic development and trade. However, the EU in general, and EaP in particular, still lack adequate power in the Caucasus (Delcour, 2012, p.15). And, while the EaP has made progress in key areas, there are numerous challenges, like Russian dominance and the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict that hinder the EaP from reaching its full potential. Therefore, for the ENP/EaP to further develop so as to increase EU influence in the region, it must take into consideration the requirements of Armenia such as including a plan-of-action over the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict and understanding that Armenia would most likely continue to hedge between the EU and Russia.

AZERBAIJAN: Beyond Oil and Water

By ALEXANDER BORUM

Alexander Borum is an MSc candidate and research and project assistant at the Netherlands Institute of International Relations Clingendael. His research focuses on diplomacy, conflict prevention and both conventional and non-traditional security, particularly climate security and private sector integration into contemporary conflicts.

The purpose of this explorative research is to underline the shortcomings of the approach taken by the EU in dealing with Azerbaijan as a strategically important neighbour. Initially, the article provides a brief framework of the situation before underlining the key areas of EU interests in approaching Azerbaijan. Specifically, these interests can be classified into peace and stability, domestic Azeri improvements, and energy security for the EU. The article continues to emphasise the current challenges to closer relations with Azerbaijan but also notes a possible opportunity for the EU to seize regarding the rentier-based Azeri economy. It also outlines the challenges posed by dwindling oil prices and by future movements towards low-carbon economies. Together with a more adaptive diplomatic strategy these changes may switch the power-relations in favour of the EU and ensure more fruitful negotiations for both parties.

INTRODUCTION

Azerbaijan might not have the longest history as an independent nation, as for hundreds of years it was but a province under empires such as the Safavid Dynasty, the Russian Empire and later the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics, with only two meagre years of independence until the fall of the Soviet Union. Azerbaijan finally reached a state of sustainable independence in 1991, but similar to many other former East-bloc states it found itself hard-pressed to re-establish and reinvent itself after ties with Moscow were formally cut (Azerbaijan - Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 2016; OWNO, 2016).

Figure 1

MAP OF AZERBAIJAN (CIA, 2018)

As a nation, Azerbaijan's location makes it the geographic link between South-Caucasus and Southwestern-Asia by the Caspian Sea. With a population of close to 10 million inhabitants, primarily Shia Muslims, it is the 4th largest Turkic nation in the world (CIA, 2016). Within its borders two regions stand out due to their unique statuses (CIA, 2016). The first region is the remote satellite; the Nakhichevan autonomous republic. The second region is the breakaway region of Nagorno-Karabakh, which since a 1994 ceasefire has operated with de facto independence from the central government in Baku (OWNO, 2016). The territorial issues are, however, not all that plagues Azerbaijan, since negative developments regarding democratic legitimacy due to a systemic suppression of free speech, the detainment of critical journalists and activists have occurred as well (Freedom House, 2015; Freedom House, 2016a; Freedom House, 2016b). Furthermore, the recurring claims of systematic corruption by the Aliyev regime surfaced and manifested in the 'Panama Papers' in which the Aliyev family is prominently featured in various capacities (Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty, 2016) all come to underline the immense levels of systemic concerns. These issues and the earlier characteristics clearly define Azerbaijan as a nation that, from the perspective of the European Union, requires both guidance and direction to return to a path that fits European wishes for a stable, democratic and progressive neighbourhood. These wishes are, however, not necessarily shared by all. In particular, the Aliyev regime opposes any notion of undermining their grip over the avenues of power in Baku and, luckily for them, Azerbaijan holds a few valuable boons as leverage in negotiations with the EU: its strategic location and direct access to natural resources in the form of oil, gas and rare earth metals (CIA, 2016). These assets form the basis of the vested interests of the outside world in the ongoing developments of Azerbaijan, setting the stage for the EU approaches to Azerbaijan and framing the perspective of third parties.

EU INTERESTS

At their core, the EU's interests can be boiled down to three key categories. First and foremost, the field of "Peace and Stability", mainly in regard to the ongoing frozen conflict between the Azeri government and the breakaway region of Nagorno-Karabakh, who sees heavy support by the neighbouring country Armenia (EEAS, 2015c, pp. 3-10). Secondly, the sustained "Domestic Developments" of Azerbaijan, in regard to human rights issues, democratic legitimacy, economic developments and positivistic social engineering (EEAS, 2015c, pp. 3-10). Lastly, the sustained interests in maintaining close cooperation between the EU and Azerbaijan in regard to "Energy" security (EEAS, 2015c, pp. 3-10).

The interests in domestic developments are a quite standardized approach the European Union often uses when dealing with its immediate neighbourhood. Both economic and societal developments as well as the subsequent cooperative agreements between the EU proper and the ENP member states are seen as crucial methods for creating stable surroundings around the Union's outer borders (European Commission, 2015e, pp. 3-6).

Interests in Peace and Stability are another regularly occurring topic. Still, in the case of Azerbaijan it must be noted that its involvement in a frozen conflict and its status within the framework of EU Energy Security does create a deeper focus on finding a solution to the ongoing issues. This is particularly the case to ensure the stability of the ongoing processes of establishing one of the potential pipeline projects such as the defunct Nabucco Pipeline¹, the TAP² or the ITGI³ because they are seen as paramount to reducing the dependence on Russian Energy within the European Union (Paul & Rzayeva, 2011, pp. 1-2).

EU FOREIGN POLICY

As such, the European Union maintains its interests in a variety of fields when it comes to dealing with Azerbaijan. These interests have naturally shaped the interactions between the two parties and, due their nature, are likely to dictate the EU-Azerbaijan relations for the foreseeable future. This is further underlined in the primary interaction platform; the ENP Action Plan, currently employed to dictate the interrelations between the two parties, supported by concurrent yet distinct approaches such as the Eastern Partnership or the European Neighbourhood Instru-

1 The Nabucco Pipeline, also known as the Nabucco-West pipeline or the Turkey-Austria Pipeline, is a potential natural gas pipeline that would transfer gas from Iraq, Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan and Egypt to the EU. Its fate is heavily debated as the project has been aborted (Baghirov, 2015). Nonetheless the concept remains a recurring topic in EU energy security under various guises (Baghirov, 2015).

2 The TAP or Trans-Adriatic Pipeline is another possible pipeline to transport gas from the Caspian Sea to the EU (Trans Adriatic Pipeline AG, 2015).

3 The ITGI or Turkey-Greece-Italy interconnector is a partly completed pipeline system that currently connects Greece and Turkey but awaits the developments of the TAP or similar projects to transport gas from the Caspian Sea to the EU (EUBAM, 2014).

ment initiatives.

ENP

The EU Action Plan for Azerbaijan is made up of fifty-five individual interest points all of which are divided over ten priority areas of the EU Action Plan (EEAS, 2015c, pp. 3-10). For Azerbaijan these interest points can be carefully categorized into three central themes, namely “Peace and Stability”, “Domestic Improvements” and “Energy Security”. Based on these categories, we can establish a visual representation of the focus-per-interest-point indicator, as seen in Figure 2.⁴

Figure 2

FIGURE 2: DIVISION OF INTEREST POINTS. THE FIGURE SHOWS THE DIVISION OF SPECIFIC INTEREST POINTS IN THE EU-AZERBAIJAN ACTION PLAN. PEACE & STABILITY: 14 POINTS; DOMESTIC IMPROVEMENTS: 36 POINTS, ENERGY SECURITY: 4 POINTS (EEAS, 2015A).

Using Figure 2, we have a strong visual guideline of where the focus of the EU efforts lays, based on the links between the three categories and the individual sub-plots of the ten-point priority list found in the EU Action Plan. Most entries in the plan are thematic in nature by default and correspond well to the categories. However, certain sub-plots have noticeable tie-ins between multiple fields. Details of these can be found in the below rundown of the priority list.

PEACE AND STABILITY

While mainly focused on the ongoing conflict over the Nagorno-Karabakh region, the “Peace and Stability” category is by no means limited to this sole area. Rather, it is comprised of three key areas involving both traditional and non-traditional security concerns based on the following Action Plan priority areas:

Priority area 1 – A peaceful solution to the Nagorno-Karabakh conflict

The first area is directed at the ongoing efforts to provide a peaceful solution to the Na-

gorno-Karabakh conflict through various means, including the OSCE Minsk Group, UN Security Council and the EUSR. A key objective within this area is to encourage dialogue between not only the different actors in the conflict but also the domestic audience (EEAS, 2015c, p. 3).

Priority area 9 – Improvements to cooperation in regards to justice and border control

The ninth area is strictly focused on ensuring the continuous improvements of the Azeri borders with a specific focus on customs (EEAS, 2015c, pp. 8-9). As this is a recurring theme within the ENP framework, it is also very inclusive of different internal and external institutions such as EUBAM (i.e. the EU Border Assistance Mission to Moldova and Ukraine) or GUAM (i.e. the cooperation between Georgia, Ukraine, Azerbaijan and Moldova) (EUBAM, 2014b).

Priority area 10 – Reinforce regional cooperation

The tenth and final area focuses on improving the cooperative bonds within the Caspian Sea regions through regional organizations dealing with law enforcement, environment and education (EEAS, 2015c, pp. 9-10).

DOMESTIC IMPROVEMENTS

As one might expect, the area of “Domestic Improvements” is a rather immense collection of approaches to improve the overall conditions for both Azerbaijan and its people. Many of these approaches are similar to broader approaches taken within the ENP or Eastern Partnership framework and serve mainly to address concerns of human security, democratic issues, economic growth and societal developments.

Priority area 2 – Strengthen Democracy

The second area is focused on increasing the transparency of electoral processes within Azerbaijan and ensuring that international election standards are adhered to. The continued focus on legislative and administrative reforms within the domestic setting is a notable priority (EEAS, 2015c, p. 4).

Priority area 3 – Protection of Human Rights

The third area is mainly concerned with the ongoing issues with the judiciary system in Azerbaijan (EEAS, 2015c, p. 4). Moreover, this area highlights further developments in regard to upholding human rights within the justice system and ensuring freedom of information, multi-religious and multi-cultural respect as well as taking a stance against inhumane treatment (EEAS, 2015c, p. 4).

Priority area 4 – Improvements to business and investments

The fourth area is focused on a number of key areas that could be seen to provide a better overall basis for foreign direct investments and business opportunities. The main efforts are anti-corruption and increasing the attractiveness of establishing businesses within the Azeri system, mainly by easing the process-train that various entrepreneurs need to go through plus a more transparent tax systems (EEAS, 2015c, p. 5).

⁴ Division of specific interest points in the EU-Azerbaijan Action Plan. Peace & Stability: 14 points; Domestic Improvements: 36 points, Energy Security: 4 points (EEAS, 2015a).

Priority area 5 – Improvements to customs quality

The fifth area is entirely focused on improvements to the Azeri customs code, specifically concerning the regulatory and executive processes through the adoption of EU/International standards (EEAS, 2015c, p. 6).

Priority area 6 – Support to sustained economic developments and diversification

The sixth area is by far the heaviest with respect to both scope and scale. It is tasked with public finance reforms, development goals, privatization of strategic enterprises, reforms to social security systems, health sector reforms, regional developments, and human resource developments. It also includes expanding efforts to restructure and improve the state's oil sector in order to conform to international standards (EEAS, 2015c, pp. 6-7).

Priority area 7 – Merging economic legislative and administrative praxis

The seventh area is entirely focused on market monitoring of various forms, adherence to intellectual property rights legislation and the enforcement hereof, together with sustained reforms within the field of public investment (EEAS, 2015c, p. 7).

ENERGY SECURITY

Only a single interest-point falls directly under an energy related framework, despite it being a central topic of internal EU considerations when dealing with Azerbaijan. Yet, while only addressed briefly in a direct fashion, we must still acknowledge the fact that the previous categories have a number of effects for establishing stable bilateral energy relations between the two actors. Energy exports and transits cannot take place without stability in the Azeri backyard which, in turn, requires both domestic and security related developments to ensure the sustainability of any pipeline projects involving Azerbaijan.

Priority area 8 – Reinforce EU-Azeri energy cooperation

The eighth area is focused on solidifying the ongoing strategic partnership between the EU and Azerbaijan with respect to the energy sector through domestic, regional and international approaches (EEAS, 2015c, p. 8).

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

As these specificities indicate, the European Union has taken a multifaceted approach to dealing with Azerbaijan. While this is primarily done through the EEAS and the Directorate-Generals under the EU Commission for the direct ENP interactions, it has also been conducted through the participatory status of the European Commission in external approach such as the OSCE Minsk Group (Klever, 2013, pp. 5-6), or more direct tools such as the EIDHR (EEAS, 2014b; Eastern Partnership - Civil Society Forum, 2015), the EUSR for South-Caucasus, or the crisis in Georgia (EEAS, 2015b). However, while the previously mentioned group of interlinked EU institutions does form a kind of holy trinity in regards to dealing with Azerbaijan, we cannot disregard the role of the EU Council when it comes to the oversight of ongoing efforts and, as an internal

actor, regarding the decision-making process that forms the basis for more direct interactions. Furthermore, in response to the systemic breaches of human rights in recent years (European Parliament, 2015), we must also acknowledge the role of the EU Parliament, which can be seen in a more instructive and directive role during last year's resolution towards Azerbaijan.

Yet, despite a thorough approach to dealings with Azerbaijan, it is noted both in the EU's annual report (European Commission, 2015c, pp. 2-14), but also in academic reviews on the ongoing process (see Merabishvili, 2015, p. 2) that negotiations between the two parties have come to a grinding halt in certain areas. The main challenge here is the skewed relationship between the relative values of what is offered and what is given in return. So, while the Azeri government in Baku might have a keen interest in exporting energy to Europe, a commodity the EU desperately needs, the government also knows full well that Europe needs the import much more than Azerbaijan needs the export (Merabishvili, 2015, pp.7-9). This has resulted in a deteriorating situation in certain policy areas, primarily with respect to implementing democratic and human rights reforms. The central government knows that it is in a position of power and can thus reject EU proposals with limited fallout (Merabishvili, 2015, pp.7-9).

As this development indicates, we are experiencing a borderline, normative fiasco in regard to the bilateral relationship; which is severely underlined by the fact that Azerbaijan has declined signing an association agreement with the EU and rather wishes to pursue its own narrower agenda in terms of formalized relations. As such, EU influences over domestic developments are destined to be marginalized in the future (Trend News Agency, 2014). Moreover, there is an apparent lack of will to adapt and overcome the current challenges, as could be seen during the visit of EU High Representative Frederica Mogherini to Baku earlier this year where she received heavy critique on her lack of stance on Azeri human rights violations, despite the EU's clear mission statement when it comes to human rights and democratization processes (European Council, 2015b; Human Rights House Network, 2016). However, during Mogherini's visit it was made clear that negotiations between the two parties would not be ceased and as such preliminary negotiations are set to continue (News.Az, 2016). Consequently, the salvation for the European Union may be presenting itself in the aftermath of the dwindling oil prices and inflation that have caused havoc in the Azeri economy (Salimova, 2016). These developments may indeed prove to be a means of leverage for the EU in its ongoing negotiations with the Aliyev regime. In fact, it is apparent that the regime might be more willing to compromise on its assertive hard-line stance in the hopes that closer relations with the European Union will indeed bring the stabilizing effects of a more diversified Azeri economy. Nonetheless, unless the EU steps up its game it is unlikely that a major breakthrough will occur any time soon. This is particularly due to the fact that the EU's reputation as a strong regional actor has been severely undermined over the last decade by a clear inability to respond effectively to Russian incursions in the region, notably during the 2008 Russo-Georgian War and the 2014 Annexation of Crimea. Similarly, its reputation has been damaged by the failed intervention politics in the Azeri backyard where a focus on Turkish-Armenian relations has taken precedence over the ongoing Nagorno-Karabakh conflict. On the side of Azerbaijan, these shortcomings have left little trust in the European Union's ability to ensure the sovereignty, security and peacebuilding efforts which it so adamantly claims to defend.

CONCLUSION

It is clear that not everything is perfect when it comes to building a closer relationship between the European Union and Azerbaijan. Nonetheless, while it is expectedly a strenuous move to go beyond the apparent challenges it is by no means impossible. Still, it is a clear case of *ex nihilo nihil fit*, where stern inward reflection must be followed by a new level of tailored approaches to bridge the differences in interests between the EU and their Azeri counterparts. Without a dedicated and concise approach to the ongoing negotiations, it is clear that the Azeri will remain able to dictate the direction for the future relationship between the two parties as they, despite the economic situation, will be able to retain a relative power position. As such, it becomes paramount for the EU to reconsider its approaches and seeks to expand its leverage options beyond its otherwise strong normative leverage,⁵ as it is clear that Azeri faith in the EU is lacking in this area. More importantly, the focus should be on establishing mutually beneficial approaches, addressing the economic concerns Azerbaijan is experiencing at the moment, and outlining how a closer relationship will both benefit the EU as well as serve to ensure long-term progress, security, and sovereignty for the Azeri people. As such, it is indeed clear that it will be possible for the European Union and Azerbaijan to reach a zone of possible agreement as there is a distinct overlap in interests; however, the deciding factor will require a reshuffle of the relative power in negotiations and the re-establishment of an atmosphere of commonalities and mutual interest. This is an overall challenge *vis-à-vis* the EU and its rather rigid ENP approach where cases like Azerbaijan stands out as examples of how readapting to more flexible approaches could lead to more successful negotiations, seeking out the negotiation ripeness that we may already now be seeing from the Azeri side. The key question, however, remains whether the European Union can react on time or whether this situation will end up being yet another wasted opportunity.

MOROCCO: Political Price for Economic Strive

By SIEPKE VAN KEULEN and CARL TOBIAS REICHERT

Siepke van Keulen is an MSc candidate and Student Assistant to prof. Herman Schaper, the former Permanent Representative of the Netherlands to the UN in New York, and to NATO. Previously, she graduated from the University of Amsterdam with a Bachelor of Cultural Anthropology and Development Sociology. She is interested in interdisciplinary research of transcultural disputes.

Carl Tobias Reichert is an MSc candidate and Student Assistant to Jaap de Hoop Scheffer, the former Secretary-General of NATO. He holds a Bachelor Degree in Political Science from the University of Hamburg. His research focuses on the EU and its foreign policy. He has also published on European electoral voting behaviour and the Brexit.

Morocco has been a member of the ENP since 1996 and is the first country to be granted the advanced status. Furthermore, Morocco receives the largest share of the ENI funds, amounting to a maximum of €890 million. The ENP has had a significant impact on the Moroccan economy, yet the impact on political and civil freedom is questionable. Additionally, the question of the Western Sahara Conflict has not been solved and little attempts have been made to contribute to a peaceful solution and a closer regional integration. As long as the ENP focuses primarily on the economy rather than political and civil liberties, it will not contribute to 'creating a ring of friends'.

INTRODUCTION

Relations between the European Union (EU) and Morocco date back to a bilateral accord signed in 1969 and received a major push in 1996 with the adoption of an association accord and membership of the European Neighborhood Policy (ENP) (European Commission, 2013). In 2008, Morocco made a qualitative leap and was subsequently granted 'advanced status' within the ENP. It was the first country of the ENP members to have this status and in 2013 the Council of the European Union published a joint proposal for a Council Decision regarding "the adoption of a recommendation on the implementation of the EU-Morocco Action Plan (AP) implementing the 'advanced status' (2013-2017)" (EUR-Lex, 2013). This advanced status consists of a broadened partnership and the inclusion of new stakeholders such as the EU-Morocco joint parliamentary committee and the EU-Morocco European economic and social committee partnership. The objectives of the plan focus on commitments to shared values on political, economic and institutional reforms (Commission of the European Communities, 2004a, p. 3).

⁵ "Normative leverage is the skillful use of standards, norms, and coherent positioning to gain advantage or protect a position." (Shell, 2006, p. 44)